

The harmful side of humour: the case of humourist Anónimo García against the Spanish judicial system (and against common sense, too)

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Abstract

Humour studies have paid some attention to the risky nature of the professional activity of satirists in non-democratic societies, where legal censorship and political persecution are prevalent. Moreover, a growing number of studies has recently focused on the legal adjudication of satire in democratic societies, where freedom of expression through satirical humour can sometimes conflict with other equally important rights. Since it is not easy to unequivocally assess the effects of a humorous practice, the comedian's own ethics of responsibility plays an important role in determining the appropriateness of satire, non in abstract but through specific situations. The case of the Spanish satirist Anónimo García exemplifies the ethics of responsibility that can be demanded of comedians. The objective of this paper will be to analyse the tension that this case has provoked, on the one hand, in the sphere of the Spanish judicial system and, on the other, in the sphere of the public debate in Spain. These are two intersecting spheres based on different principles. Sometimes they overlap, sometimes they oppose each other, sometimes they run parallel. This case exemplifies the problems involved in the relationship between freedom of expression and certain forms of humour, when they conflict with the democratic values that aspire to create a society oriented toward minimising harm.

Keywords: Anónimo García, freedom of expression, satire, humour and the law, humour and the internet.

1. The responsibility of the comedian

In a recent essay on the centenary of Max Weber's famous lecture *Politik als Beruf* [Politics as a Vocation], the philosopher Wendy Brown reflected on the German thinker's lessons that are still applicable today in twenty-first century societies (Brown, 2023). Brown agrees with Weber, pointing to the great danger that still haunts modernity. As argued by Weber, a nihilistic trend – and its inseparable counterpart: sectarian and tribal dogmatism – emerges when a paradigm underpinning the order of the world (in the past it was religion, but today it is also science) is

deprived of its status as an absolute truth. In the political sphere, Weber's proposed solution to circumvent this danger consists of appealing to a type of politician who must fulfil a Faustian mission. Such a politician must charismatically seek the support of a part of their population to win elections, but after that they must govern for the whole of the population, with the challenge of minimally satisfying everyone and, in the end, not completely satisfying anyone. What does it mean to be applauded and voted for by some people, while knowing at the same time that you must govern for all the citizens of a country? This prospect entails sacrificing charisma in favour of routine, and subordinating one's convictions to something much more important -namely the ethics of responsibility in the exercise of one's profession. It is precisely this trade-off space that Nunner-Winkler calls the "grey zone of legitimate dissent" (Nunner-Winkler, 2020, p. 184), characterised by a kind of post-sceptical rational spirit that flees both sectarianism and cynical anti-social distrust, allowing societies to function as such. This grey area exists and grows when people are suspicious of excessively dogmatic and sacred views on any issue, understand that disputes always demand a high level of deliberative reflexivity and, above all, recognise that harm minimisation should be the main ethical horizon of any decent society.

Bridging the gap between the world of politics and humorous activities on a public level, the aim of this essay is to explore the possibilities and the advantages (but also the challenges) involved in thinking about an *ethics of responsibility* applied to the world of satirists and, in general, to any producer of humour practices that aim to have a social impact (Wilk & Gimbel, 2024). This ethics of responsibility would be connected with recent changes that some authors have called the *repoliticisation of humour* (Nieuwehuis & Zijp, 2022). According to these authors, humour "cannot be reduced to a single political value such as freedom of expression" and claim that humour "is always political in the sense that it is embedded in relationships of power, and contributes to the formation of identities" (Nieuwehuis & Zijp, 2022, p. 343). Paradoxically, this concept of repoliticisation, associated with the idea of responsibility, has taken very different paths. In some cases, this "responsibility" has consisted of claiming the work of humourists as if they were the last sacred apostles of the West, prophets charged with safeguarding the supreme value of humour and freedom of speech, our "liberal regime of humour" (Kuipers, 2011), against a multitude of enemies who, lacking any sense of humour (as puritanical leftists or ethnic and religious communities opposed to the secular values of the West) put our political system, our freedoms and our sense of humour at risk. It is interesting to observe how this argument of political risk towards humour has developed in recent decades. A humour scholar such as Christie Davies thought that a Weberian ethic of responsibility applied to the work of humourists did not make much sense (Davies, 1992). However, in the wake of the scandal of the Mohammed cartoons in 2005, he pointed out that the problem was that although humour "does not give offence, its recipients take offence (...) and use it without scruple as the basis for synthetic indignation and political mobilisation" (Davies, 2008, p. 6). Ironically, those who today defend humour practices such as those that featured the Mohammed cartoons appeal to a highly politicised ethics of conviction (and they also believe that this can be an act of political responsibility).

On the other hand, the repoliticisation of humour has led to a more widespread awareness of its political affordances. As numerous studies have shown, humour and especially some humorous activities such as satire have important social functions and, therefore, its degree of social neutrality is questionable (Jenkins, 1994). In light of these studies, it is clear that humour can perpetuate stereotypes and legitimise discourses of domination, but it can also promote social change or important public deliberations on issues of general interest agree. This suggests that there is some degree of responsibility on the part of the humourists for his or her actions, and that it is therefore possible to demand a type of ethics in accordance with the social impact of this activity. In this approach, however, it is important to distinguish what kind of ethics of responsibility is attributable to the humourist. If the intentions and effects of his or her actions

are diffuse and unconscious, are measurable in the long term, have an impact on large audiences and can be assessed ambivalently, the ethics of responsibility would be generic. If, on the other hand, the relationship between the causes and effects of such actions offer clear, concrete evidence, are measurable in the short term, are aimed at personalised audiences and can be assessed in a concrete way, either positively or negatively, then the ethics of responsibility would be more specific. In the case of politicians, the ethics of responsibility is evaluated in a more or less institutionalised way through the mechanism of elections and, therefore, the generic and specific responsibility for their actions are fused in that same ritual act. However, in the case of humourists, the mechanisms for evaluating the responsibility of their actions would be very different: on the one hand, there is the generic responsibility that is registered through public approval or rejection; on the other hand, there is the specific responsibility that is determined by a possible ruling in the judicial sphere. As we shall see, the existence of these two paths, which may ignore, overlap or directly contradict each other in their dynamics and results, has greatly complicated the attribution of an ethics of responsibility to the activity of humour.

The following sections analyse a specific case in Spain to study the scope of this supposed ethics of responsibility for a comedian and the consequences of the explicit acceptance of this ethics in the sphere of public opinion and in the judicial sphere. Based on a detailed description of the case, known both by the name of the satirist –working under the pseudonym *Anónimo García*– and by the humorous action carried out –the creation of a satirical website called *El Tour de la Manada* [The Wolf Group Tour]– four dimensions will be analysed: (i) the scope of freedom of speech and its relationship with humour; (ii) the importance of context when producing and interpreting humour; (iii) the relationship between humour and the possible harm caused to specific people; and (iv) the role of the judicial system in the resolution of controversies arising from the use of humour.

2. *Anónimo García and The Wolf Group Tour*

The satirical website *El Tour de la Manada* (*The Wolf Group Tour*) was created on 3 December 2018 in the midst of a political, judicial and social storm in Spain concerning a gang-rape scandal that was still being tried in court at that time.¹ The sequence of events is relevant to understand the impact of this satirical website. In July 2016, an event occurred that shocked the Spanish public: during the celebration of the world-famous Sanfermines festival in Pamplona, a group of five men (known since then as *La Manada: The Wolf Group*) raped a young woman and recorded a series of videos that were later circulated on various social media networks. The young woman sued the rapists and in April 2018 they were each sentenced in the local court to nine years in prison for the crime of sexual abuse (not sexual assault, as requested by the victim, who appealed the ruling because she argued that this non-consensual sexual act had been carried out with violence and intimidation). On 5 December 2018, and just two days after the publication of the satirical website by *Anónimo García*, this ruling was upheld by the High Court of Justice of Navarre (TSJN), to the astonishment and indignation of a significant part of the public, both in Spain and internationally, who considered this case an example of a sexual assault, not sexual abuse. The victim appealed again against the ruling and finally in June 2019 the Supreme Court agreed with her, stating that the crime had been sexual assault, that is, rape with violence and intimidation, and that therefore the ruling should be 15 years in prison for the members of *La Manada*.

¹ All the information about the case of *Wolf Group Tour*, told from *Anónimo García*'s perspective, can be found on the website (www.tourdelamanada.com). Information about the controversy, with all the articles published in favour of *Anónimo García*, none against him, can be seen on the author's own website (www.homovelamine.com/tag/tour-la-manada).

On 3 December 2018, while the public was awaiting the TSJN ruling, a comic activist calling himself Anónimo García published a website called *El Tour de la Manada*, which offered a tour of the places in Pamplona where the 2016 rape took place, including the hotel where the rapists stayed, the sale of T-shirts and other objects that directly alluded to the incident, without making it clear whether the website was serious or not. The website also included the following text:

“Amidst alcohol and debauchery, five men in the latest hairstyles met a young woman in the central Plaza del Castillo. Barely 20 minutes later, they entered a doorway 300 meters away and sexually assaulted her. What happened in those 20 minutes? Where did the attackers go afterward? How did the police identify them? Find out everything on this tour!”

The website was shut down three days later without the exact reasons for such a decision being known, whether it was its potential impact on the court decision or on the social media scandal (Trillo, 2018). However, the takedown was accompanied by a statement from the author, declaring that the website was intended as a “media bomb” in order to expose “how the media pounce like hyenas on any corpse whose still-warm blood they can suck”. The author of the website has not clarified his reasons any further, although he has acknowledged that he is very proud of the social impact of his website (García, 2019). The rape victim, who had contacted her doctor to express her discomfort at the impact of the website on her, and whose discomfort was later confirmed by a medical report diagnosing a relapse in her mental health, filed a criminal complaint against the author of the website for hate crime (art. 510 of the Spanish Criminal Code) and for the crime of degrading treatment (art. 173.1).

In December 2019, the Criminal Court of First Instance in Pamplona sentenced Anónimo García to an 18-month prison sentence and a fine of 15,000 euros for the crime of degrading treatment. In June 2020, the TSJN confirmed the sentence and, in November 2020, the Supreme Court, the court of final arbitration in Spain, dismissed the appeal of Anónimo García and upheld the ruling, which was definitive at that time. In January 2021, he filed an appeal for protection at the Spanish Constitutional Court (TC), claiming that these rulings violated his fundamental rights because he understood that his ironic performance was within the framework of the freedom of speech (García, 2024) enshrined in the Spanish Constitution. This is the first case in Spain where someone who had been denounced to the courts by another person, and not by the public authorities, has been sentenced by a court ruling through criminal (rather than civil) proceedings, due to an action or expression in which humour played a central role. Four years later, in May 2025, the Constitutional Court (TC) overturned Anónimo García's conviction, thereby protecting his freedom of speech (STC 117/2025, p. 81390). The Constitutional Court stressed that the website's “declared intention was to criticise the way in which the media covers certain newsworthy events”; moreover, it “did not contain any single reference to the victim [...], and displayed the Government of Navarra's logo against gender-based violence” (STC 117/2025, p. 81389).

To understand and properly evaluate this satirical website, it is important to profile its creator. In an interview in 2017, Anónimo García presented himself as a founding member of an anti-dogmatic collective committed to cultural agitation and “culture jamming” called Homo Velamine. His group carried out comic actions to annoy and ridicule, in a somewhat hooliganish way, any form of moralistic and puritanical thought, with a focus on not only but largely left-wing discourse, through physical performances and flashmobs. In fact, the *Wolf Group Tour* website was his first mayor online comedy intervention, unlike his previous, distinctly offline performances. Inspired by values and a supposedly progressive militancy (Anónimo García had worked for Greenpeace until he was fired after the conviction), he defines himself *à la Bergson* as an *ultrarationalist*: he denounces the mainstream rationality in our societies as too sentimental, claiming that it fails to detect the contradictions and absurdities of life, and that this

fact is affecting our sense of humour (San Román, 2017, p. 78-83). Unlike other types of activists, such as the *Yes Men*, who in their performances use humour to denounce abuses by groups in power, or the more politically oriented type of humorous performances, such as the theatre of Bertold Brecht, the humorous actions of Anónimo García are closer to Situationism, Dada or Surrealism, with a hooliganish, carefree, festive and apparently depoliticised touch (after all, he self-identifies as a left-wing activist who is criticising the puritanism and supposed dogmatism of the left).² In his opinion, a revealing example of this progressivist puritanism would be the gender agenda, which has been a source of comedy in several of his interventions,³ right up to the aforementioned satirical website of *The Wolf Group Tour*.

The trial, subsequent rulings and final acquittal of Anónimo García for the publication of the satirical website has generated an enormous amount of attention, both on social media networks and in conventional media. On social networks, the diagnosis and assessment of the case were much more favourable towards Anónimo García, while in traditional media opinions were much more divided.⁴ A simple internet search reveals a myriad of entries on the case, which largely favour Anónimo García and, to a much lesser extent, the victim's perspective. Some academic articles have also been written, mostly by jurists, who have analysed the judgement in the case mainly in judicial terms (Cigüela, 2021; Cuerda, 2021), while other scholars have analysed the case from sociological and cultural perspectives (Herrero Moreno, 2020). The 2022 publication of a book about the case, written by the cultural critic Juan Soto Ivars, which quickly becoming a bestseller and received an essay prize in 2024, helped to raise awareness of the case and, above all, to defend Anónimo García as the public victim of an alleged social hunt ('woke' leftism, punitive feminism, cancel culture) and of questionable judicial decisions until the TC ruling (judges being excessively partial to supposed gender-agenda arguments, and much more hesitant to defend freedom of expression). After his conviction and especially after the ruling of the Spanish Constitutional Court, Anónimo García has publicly defended his actions, even though this has put him at risk of being instrumentalised by certain right-wing political discourses with which he apparently disagrees (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 195). In his defence, he has claimed that the *main* aim of the satirical website was not so much to provoke laughter, but rather to denounce the sensationalism with which the media and the public in general focus their interest on this type of public scandals. This argument, still used today by him, is very important to understand the reasons why this type of dark humour, although it aspired to sarcastically criticise the way media talk about sexual scandals, ultimately fell flat - arguably to the point of constituting disparaging dark humour towards the victim of this sinister event (on the distinction between sarcastic and disparaging dark humour, see Godioli, 2024, p. 140).

Paradoxically, the satirical website itself would have been a scandalous and unfunny reflection of what it was supposedly criticising. While waiting for the Constitutional Court's ruling, which took almost four years to be published, Anónimo García, showing his fatigue and perhaps despondency at the situation, described himself as a "shoddy cynic"⁵ who found it very difficult to believe in justice. He claimed, therefore, that it made no sense to demand any kind of ethics of responsibility for the action carried out and, for this very reason, he affirmed that he

² For an excellent comparative analysis of the various "humorous political stunts" and humour political activism, with their dilemmas and risks, see Sorensen (2016).

³ See, for example, the video explaining and self-promoting his activities (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Vf8z3_gyvvM), uploaded in March 2024, which has hundreds of comments, the vast majority in favour of the author himself.

⁴ The progressive Spanish press has focused the news mainly on the consequences of the satirical action on the victim, while the conservative press has focused the news mainly on the supposed non-existence of the Tour and the attacks on freedom of expression. To get an idea of the controversy between progressive and conservative commentators and opinion makers on the case, see Simón (2024).

⁵ See the revealing interview of Anónimo García with a right-wing libertarian journalist named Marina De la Torre, where he points out how this case has turned him into a "shoddy cynic" / "cínico de pacotilla": 1h:01':09" (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RdlwLclwTE8>).

could not understand anything that has happened. After the TC ruling, Anónimo García said that “yes, now I believe in justice”. He stated: “finally, I’m no longer a criminal” (García, 2025). This statement implies that, in his view, judicial rulings are the only thing that matters in this case. In this article, however, we assume that judicial decisions are only part of the story.

3. Freedom of speech and common sense

Freedom of speech has served as the main practical support for humour in modern liberal societies, especially when humorous practices have been subject to scrutiny, criticism, regulation, or even legal challenges (Heinze, 2016; Mchangama, 2022; Godioli et al., 2025). As Bricker observes, during the 18th century in England, the back-and-forth between regulators (through parliamentary legislation and judicial rulings) and satirists (through their supposed ‘libels’) shaped both the law and literary practices. This relationship allows us to understand (i) what was the type of humour that was politically acceptable to public authorities, and (ii) what was the real capacity of these legal and regulatory tools (Bricker, 2022, p. 261-262).

This connection between humour and freedom of speech, as we know in modern times, began to be consolidated at the beginning of the 19th century in the context of a society that was embracing the values of political pluralism and individualistic liberalism. As part of the historical development of the liberal-democratic model, the battle to expand freedom of speech and to guarantee public recognition of a more plural, critical, satirical and challenging humour towards established values, has been gaining ground, despite differences among the legal systems of various countries (Godioli & Little, 2022). As Godioli & Young (2023) argue in an international comparative study of dozens of court cases linking freedom of speech and humour, international human rights law today tends to protect humorous expression (including potentially offensive or provocative humour) about topics that were considered off-limits in the past—such as political leaders, institutions, or religious beliefs (Godioli & Young, 2023). To be sure, this protection is far from unconditional, as humour is sometimes seen by courts as a disguise for harmful expression such as incitement to hostility, discrimination and violence (Godioli et al., 2022, p. 2247). However, the general trend in the judicial field and in public opinion is that humorous expression should in principle be protected, thanks to its association with the supreme value of freedom of speech. It is worth remembering that, in some cases, this attitude may be favoured by a “comic innocence” (Zijp, 2024) view of humour, whereby humour—even in its disparaging forms—cannot cause any significant societal harm.

Historically, however, there have been other ways of understanding the relationship between freedom of expression and humour, beyond the pluralist framework. As the republicanist Quentin Skinner (1988) argues, just as there is a conception of (republican) freedom before liberalism, there is also a republican view of humour before liberalism, in which comic practices appeal to a centripetal common sense, to values shared and enjoyed by all people in the same political community. As Adam Smith states in his *Theory of Moral Sentiments*, humour would not be aimed so much at praising creative, selfish and disintegrating wit, but at valuing the reciprocal sympathy of the seller who seeks a good relationship with his buyer because it naturally helps to create bonds of community (Frazer, 2010). This perspective is currently criticised because there are reasonable doubts about the possibility, even the desirability, of achieving a kind of humorous “affective consensus” at the community level (Kuipers, 2006, p. 113-114; Assman & Detmers, 2016), as this scenario is contrary to liberal values that call for cultural pluralism and diversity in the enjoyment of humour.

Despite this resistance, however, we think that there are good reasons to consider the possibility of a humorous common sense—or, at least, some consensus on where the boundaries of humour should be drawn. Thus, for example, as Godioli & Young (2023, p. 14) point out,

courts often understandably adopt a much more restrictive stance towards freedom of humorous expression when the targets are neither celebrities nor political leaders but private individuals or particularly vulnerable, marginalised or stigmatised social groups. Why should such views find traction in both courts and public opinion if humour has, according to a certain liberal view, no practical social effect? Perhaps the opposite is more accurate: many studies of derogatory humour offer sufficient empirical evidence to show that humour can help perpetuate hatred and discrimination, as well as produce objective harm for specific individuals (Ford & Ferguson, 2004; Billig, 2005; Kotthoff, 2006; Pérez, 2022). Today, common sense in a positive way is not an option, because it seems difficult to find comical practices that are generally liked by a whole community. Nevertheless, it seems more feasible—as Rorty (1989, p. 164)—to achieve common sense consensus in a negative way, that is, to affirm that in liberal societies “cruelty is the worst thing that can happen”, so it would be convenient to try to avoid being cruel in public life. In turn, it would be possible to appeal to a certain humorous common sense if the aim of a society is “harm minimisation” (Nunner-Winkler, 2020, p. 184).

The case of Anónimo García and the *Wolf Group Tour* website illustrates the tensions between these two ways of understanding the relationship between freedom of speech and the appeal to common sense. Among the legal scholars who have studied this case, the majority have been highly critical of the previous rulings before the TC overturn, as they considered that this humorous practice should be accepted as part of the price of defending freedom of speech. As Javier Cigüela and María Luis Cuerda state, the most surprising thing in the three rulings on the case before the TC overturn is that there was not even a direct mention of this issue:

we do not find any line dedicated to freedom of speech: it is not that the victim’s right not to have her case criticised is discussed and thought to prevail here, but rather that it does not even appear as something that is at stake here.

(Cigüela, 2021, p. 482-483)

there is no reference to the rights recognised in Art. 20 of the Constitution, related to freedom of speech, in any of the three rulings, despite the fact that the lack of this preliminary examination or its implementation in disregard of the constitutional content of the right affected, constitutes in itself, in the opinion of the TC, an infringement of the fundamental rights affected.

(Cuerda, 2021, p. 503)

In a less technical and more essayistic tone, the best-selling book by Soto Ivars that studies the case stresses the same idea and highlights how this argument in favour of freedom of speech has been the one most claimed in social networks (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 172), while some conventional media, especially those closest to progressive discourses and defenders of the feminist agenda, initiated—in his opinion—a process of criminalisation of Anónimo García (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 170-171).

The truth is that all the courts before TC ruling adopted an approach centred on the victim's position of objective defencelessness in the face of the action carried out by the author of the website, who during the trial stated that he had not thought of her at any time (because otherwise, in his opinion, he would not have been able to make humour out of this fact). As the first ruling from June 2020 points out,

objectively assuming that the content of the web page objectified the victim of the sexual offence, instrumentalised and used her and her previous suffering, and disregarding the dignity of the victim, he consciously assumed as a necessary consequence the harm that he was going to cause her with the creation and publication of the page.

(Judgement 111/2020, Provincial Court of Navarra, p. 7)

In short, this ruling focuses on the lack of a minimum of common sense on the part of the comedian in carrying out this humorous act against a particularly vulnerable person to whom it would have been reasonably responsible to give some kind of consideration. The TC's argument, on the contrary, has indicated that the important thing in this case from a constitutional point of view was not to evaluate the possible social effects of the satire, but rather to evaluate the satirist's intention as it could be reasonably constructed, which was ultimately deemed compatible with the fundamental right to freedom of speech.

4. Real, virtual, fictitious and fake contexts

Alongside freedom of speech, a second element that all humour studies take into account when appreciating, enjoying, and, above all, valuing and judging a humorous practice is the analysis of the context in which it takes place (Zajdman, 1991; Saper, 1995; Crawford, 2003; Kotthoff, 2003; Martin et al., 2008; Gray & Ford, 2013; Filani, 2017; Tsakona, 2020; James & Fox, 2021). In this sense, however, as Judith Butler rightly warns, one must be extremely careful because contexts are always slippery dimensions, open to performative resignifications, where freedom of expression in certain contexts is reformulated as the freedom to hate (Butler, 2013, p. 124). A well-known example is the expression "it's only a joke" often invoked by humourists as a defensive argument against the alleged interpretative dislocation of their humorous practices, in which the context has allegedly been distorted (Kowalski, 2000; Shifman et al., 2007; Woodzicka et al., 2015; Lawless et al., 2020). Occasionally, as in the case of Anónimo García, the humourist claims that his *satirical intentions* have been taken out of context, due to misleading interpretations, which have reduced a humorous expression to an unacceptable one.

According to the literature on humour studies, the contexts in which the satirical website *The Wolf Group Tour* can be judged are of three types: (i) the temporal context, that is, when this website was produced and how far it was from the events reported there; (ii) the semantic context, that is, the specific material with which the humorous practice was made and its relationship with other similar practices carried out by its author; and finally, (iii) the relationship of this practice with what we could call the context of the real (on the role of context in the assessment of controversial humour, see Godioli et al., 2025).

From a temporal point of view, the website was published on 3 December 2018, just when the victim of the rape was awaiting a ruling from the court. Therefore, it was a moment of maximum expectation and high emotional impact, which was aggravated after the victim became aware of the aforementioned website. As in other legal cases, the courts were more likely to condemn humorous actions that took place on dates close to a particularly violent event, such as a terrorist attack, or when its publication appeared at a particularly sensitive moment in judicial deliberations (Godioli & Young, 2023, p. 21). In this instance, the publication of the website in the middle of an open judicial process demonstrates, beyond the judges' condemnation, an irresponsible indifference of Anónimo García to the consequences of his humour on either the case or its victim (Caruso, 2024, p. 27-28).

From a semantic point of view, the website provided few linguistic elements, co-textual cues (Godioli et al., 2022, p. 2256) that would have facilitated its interpretation, including its comic ambiguity. There was no reference to the website's authorship, nor was there any explicit or implicit reference to the final objective of the action, that is, the criticism of the media and its sensationalist desire to exploit such scandalous news as the gang rape of *La Manada*. There was a very brief mention of the victim of the rape ('the girl') and the only direct and clear reference on the website were to the rapists, who were described in an ambivalent way. One of the rulings noted that Anónimo García had made a "laughable treatment of La Manada", although it was unclear whether his explanations in the court about this "laughable treatment" were meant as

satirical criticism (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 186). This website was not the first humorous action in which Anónimo García dealt with issues related to the supposed gender agenda, about which he has an ambiguous relationship: although he does not particularly declare himself anti-feminist, he has expressed his opposition to the radical puritanism of a certain type of feminism in Spain (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 173-177). In short, it was not possible to determine whether the website was a satire of media sensationalism, a trivialisation of the victim's suffering, or both: there was a radical doubt as to whether or not what the website offered was to be interpreted at face value. As Soto Ivars (2022, p. 218) says,

the Tour had left it up to the public to choose the correct interpretation, and its author did not even present himself as a buffoon, which would perhaps have been a social mitigating factor, but kept himself in the shadows, as this was the only way for the act to work. For this reason, neither the literal explanations of Anónimo García at the trial, when his mask fell, nor the recant that replaced the original content days after the Tour was launched, were of any use.

The semantic context of the website offers numerous problems for its certain assessment. First, if the website had shown its facetious intent, this certainly would have increased the chance that this website could be interpreted as a humorous practice. Second, if the website offered any room for ambiguity, then the only correct interpretation was to doubt the ultimate intention of the website. And these doubts surely increased the chances of harmful interpretation, especially by those who found it inappropriate, but above all by the rape victim herself. Third, if the author wanted the website to facilitate social criticism, it is questionable whether such a minimal degree of humour justified the ultimate meaning of the website as it was presented. Fourth, it is not clear whether Anónimo García gave reliable explanations during the trial, because at different moments he expressed his surprise that a court could be judging irony. In fact, during the trial itself he made use of irony at unfortunate moments, such as his comment on the misunderstanding that has often been made of the main character in Hitchcock's *Psycho* (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 189). The judge possibly understood this comment as inappropriate and out of place, and portrayed a person of little sensitivity, incapable of thinking, even during the trial, about the damage he could have caused. Finally, if the webpage hides its real intentions, it is worth asking what these intentions actually were, and, from there, to ask whether it would not have been better to display the comedy from the first moment so that the joke/criticism would have come across as such. In fact, this concealment could be considered ethically irresponsible.

The discussion on 'what is real' in this case has certainly been one of the most interesting debates. To understand the degree of 'reality' in this case, it is worth analysing it on three levels: the real vs. the virtual; the real vs. the fictional; and the real vs. the fake. First, it is worth asking to what extent humour produced on the Internet should be considered differently from humour in the offline world (Friedler, 2002; Kuipers, 2005; Shifman, 2007, 2014; Fielitz & Thurston, 2018; Gardner et al., 2021). Second, it is worth asking to what extent humour is part of the autonomous world of cultural, artistic fiction, or, on the contrary, it is a sphere that has a certain overlap with other communicative activities, as is the case with mockumentaries (Jacobi, 2016; Wallace, 2018) or educational performances (Shrodes, 2021; Ayu et al., 2024). Finally, it is worth asking to what extent something that is only advertised on the Internet is or is not real.

The distinction between the real versus the virtual is important because humour on the Internet completely disrupts the way in which contextualisation happens. As Isabelle Touton argues through her analysis of online comments about various controversies over humour in the French satirical weekly magazine *Charlie Hebdo*, the problem lies in the fact that "the Internet allows decontextualisation" because "ignorance of the publication leads to unfair judgements" (Touton, 2016, p. 295). In fact, the Internet is not yet a new context where humour can be easily interpreted on a global level: at best, it is the realm of pure decontextualisation where millions of people share humorous content in a non-specific way; at worst, it is a place where echo

chambers are generated and where humorous content is shared in a tribal way (Garrett, 2009; Nagle, 2017). In the case of *The Wolf Group Tour* website, the decontextualisation of its meaning provoked a multitude of reactions, with many respondents being confused or angered by the site, rather than finding it funny. Fortunately, the website was shut down very quickly, just three days after its launch, which prevented the creation of tribal echo chambers in which the multiplication of supposedly humorous comments would have created a snowball with very harmful effects for the victim.

The distinction between the real and the fictitious is also important because, in this case, at stake was whether or not the website was a clearly identified artistic and cultural activity with a message of social denunciation. In this respect, it is interesting to compare the website of Anónimo García with the exhibition held in 2019 by the cultural artist Inma la Inmunda (*Inma The Filthy*) in the Spanish city of Seville, entitled *La Manada City (The Wolf Pack City)*, which critically reflects, not without humour, on what the case of the gang rape of *La Manada* had meant for the city, as the rapists were from Seville (López-Cabrales et al., 2023). It is also interesting to compare Anónimo García's website with the performance of a play that has had a great impact on public opinion in Spain, entitled *La Jauría (The Pack of Hounds)*, which the victim permitted to be produced. The doubts about the fictitious nature in the case of Anónimo García's website, unlike the two previous cases, did not allow for an adequate contextualisation, which was detrimental to its assessment as a responsible act.

But, without a doubt, the difference between what is real and what is fake has been the most controversial issue of this satirical website. Numerous media, including some legal analysts (Cigüela, 2021), echoing to a large extent the thesis sustained by Soto Ivars (2022), explained that this case should be called *The fake Tour of the Wolf Group* because it was actually judging “a Tour” that never materialised in practice, implicitly taking for granted that a web page is not real (in fact, it existed) and therefore cannot generate real consequences (Rocco, 2020, p. 140). The following dialogue between Alfonso Pérez Medina, a famous Spanish court journalist, Soto Ivars himself and a Twitter user exemplifies this axis of discussion:

Alfonso Pérez Medina: “One year and a half in prison for the creator of the Tour de la Manada, which recreated a visit to the scenes of the Sanfermines gang rape. The convicted will compensate the victim with 15,000 euros because it increased her post-traumatic stress” (1:02 p.m.—10 December 2019)

Juan Soto Ivars (in response to Alfonso Pérez Medina): “You should inform yourself better, Alfonso. That tour does not exist” (11 December 2019).

Alfonso Pérez Medina: “The website that advertised the Tour does, Juan. And the moral damage to the victim, according to the sentence, too. Maybe you are the one who is misinformed” (11 December 2019).

Pizarrín (in response to Alfonso Pérez Medina): “Another one who speaks without reading the news” (11 December 2019).

Alfonso Pérez Medina: “What I have read is the ruling” (11 December 2019)

The alleged ‘falsity’ of the *Wolf Group Tour* is justified through the idea that Anónimo García never had any intention of organising such a tourist visit, but the problem is that this website does not make it clear that this idea is merely a hypothesis. In fact, the website tries to be as credible as possible: direct allusions are made to the streets through which the rapists passed and mentions of the hotel where the rapists stayed are made (which also prompted a complaint from the hotel owners, who requested the immediate removal of this reference on the web). Only *now*, in retrospect, but not *at the time* of the website's launch, do we know that the execution of

the tour was basically a lie. This action is something different from a fake published in an online news satire, where the fake is clearly decoded by the audience. Anónimo García only admitted that the website was fake after the controversy started, not before. In December 2018, the website played with deception. But deception is not the same as lying (Dyrel, 2018): deception is always based on the idea that what is said is plausible and therefore in no way is false. In short, the website was real, as were the painful consequences for the victim.

5. Humour harms

The harmlessness of humour is often emphasised by alluding to the fact that a joke is not like a bullet: no one is known to have died from hearing a joke, however unpleasant and offensive it may be. This comparison, however, hides some situations in which humour can produce adverse social effects. That is, humour produces victims, sometimes directly and other times through longer-term cumulative harm (Bartolo & Matamoros-Fernández, 2023). Let us think, for example, of racist humour aimed against minority social groups, where hate speech and contempt are mixed with doses of comic fun to facilitate social discrimination (Billig, 2005; Romero & Cruthirds, 2006; Pérez & Ward, 2019; Pérez, 2022).

In our case study, Anónimo García's humorous satire in *The Wolf Group Tour* directly affected one specific person, who was especially vulnerable having lived through a traumatic situation, and of whom it was reasonable to think that their desire was not to want to relive it or for this painful experience to be used in a comical way. As critics of the ruling before the TC state, the desires of the victim should not preclude humour because, if this were always the case, one might ask whether “satire can be made of a case in which there are victims, or everything will depend on whether the victims feel hurt and denounce” (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 201). However, the question here is whether this humour practice was the direct cause of a real harm that can be proven by scientific or medical evidence. We would not be talking, therefore, about someone who subjectively feels hurt, in a generic way as part of a particularly vulnerable group, but about someone who objectively manifests a palpable deterioration in their health as a direct consequence of a humorous action. The courts rejected the charge of a hate crime against the group of female rape victims because it would be diffuse, ambiguous and unspecific. Instead, all the courts until TC accepted the crime of degrading treatment towards a specific person because it observed that there was a direct and negative cause-and-effect relationship towards that person.

Supposedly, as the author of the *Wolf Group Tour* later claimed, the red line in any practice of humour is not to harm the victims. But as he himself surprisingly stated during the trial, “that was easy in this case because nobody knew anything about her” (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 133) and, therefore, he could not know in advance whether or not the victim was going to see the webpage (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 204). In other words, the fact that the victim of the gang rape of La Manada has remained anonymous during these years by her express wish –which reinforces the idea that she has suffered greatly and does not want any kind of publicity– led Anónimo García to forget that this person really existed, with dehumanising consequences, as if the whole action could be summed up in a kind of duel between two abstractions: Anonymous the comedian versus Anonymous the raped woman. The prosecutor pointed out that the harm to the victim had been real, but perhaps it was more a matter of recklessness; however, the judges until the TC ruling considered that the design of the webpage involved planning, time for elaboration and reflection on the possible effects of such an action on the victim, and therefore considered that there had been an unacceptable level of disregard and irresponsibility towards the victim.

One of the most surprising things about this case has been the scant attention that social media networks and the public conversation, in general, has paid to the medical evidence

provided in the trial to determine the possible seriousness of the harm caused to the victim. There were two pieces of evidence: on the one hand, a phone call from the victim to an internist the day after the web page was published, in which she expressed her discomfort after learning the existence of the tour; on the other hand, a medical report made four months later showing a worsening of the victim's health and an aggravation of her post-traumatic stress disorder, which has been directly associated with the publication of the web page and the repercussions of this event. Despite the discussion that exists in Spain about the difficulty of empirically measuring the existence of a crime of degrading treatment (Monge, 2020; Caruso, 2024), in this case all the judges gave sufficient credibility to the testimony of the nurse and the medical evidence to establish a direct cause-and-effect relationship between the web page and the physical damage to the victim's mental health. In this regard, it is interesting to see the arguments offered by the Constitutional Court to analyse the negative effects on the health of the victim of this satirical practice. According to the TC,

the comedian's conduct had an undeniable and painful impact on the victim's feelings and caused great suffering. However, a broad scope must be granted to freedom of expression, even if its exercise may annoy, disturb, or disgust, since it constitutes the foundation of a democratic society.

(STC 117/2025, p. 81389).

Yet, while the website might amount to protected expression from a legal standpoint, some ethical considerations are in order, as will be further discussed in the next section.

What has been extensively discussed on social media is the alleged responsibilities of the rape victim, with an abundant number of comments that blame her attitude (Mina, 2024), and especially the attitude of her lawyer, accused of not being sufficiently open to negotiation during the trial, as she purportedly wanted to exploit this case to promote gender issues on the public agenda (Soto Ivars, 2022, p. 173-177). The aim of this avalanche of messages in the digital world is to try to turn Anónimo García into the real victim of the case, in the belief that the current cultural battle consists of determining who is the victim in each situation, converted from that moment into a hero/martyr (Hughes, 1994; Dalrymple, 2010; Giglioli, 2014). This creates a vicious circle in which one does not know where the very idea of victim ends and where responsibility begins.

All the rulings in the Anónimo García case, so different and even contradicting each other, arguably fall short of a fair assessment of the harm caused. In the initial rulings, the consideration of the victim's suffering led to the approval of an excessively high prison penalty; in the Constitutional Court's ruling, on the contrary, the pain caused by the humour has been undervalued because the TC's main concern was to provide legal guarantees for the protection of the fundamental right to freedom of speech. In both cases, the ruling does not seem to be based on a nuanced reflection on issues of responsibility and proportionality. It is worth asking to what extent court rulings should have mitigated the existing harm and promoted alternative solutions, allowing satirists to be accountable for an ethic of responsibility beyond the criminal sphere. As some jurists argue, this case is a symptom of the extreme judicialisation (Cigüela, 2021, p. 473) applied to issues that have to do with freedom of speech and the use of political satire. Perhaps, a more nuanced approach to these issues is only possible beyond the judicial realm.

6. Judicial power, solution or problem?

The judicial system was once conceived of as the last resort for resolving social controversies. Nowadays, it has become a common option, even the first one. Beyond the serious problem of

increased activity in the courts, this situation has perverse consequences, including, for example, a reduction in the mechanisms of social self-control over potentially conflict-driven activities, a relaxation of the ethics of responsibility *ex ante* for any concrete individual actions or an over-reliance on censorship instead of addressing institutional discrimination (Article 19, 2015). In the case of more controversial humour activities, the result is that legal regulation alone will not solve deep-seated cultural problems such as misogyny or racism; besides, over-restrictive approaches to offensive speech are likely to generate polarised responses and tap into “martyrdom narratives” on the part of bad-faith actors and hate groups (Heinze, 2016; Mchangama, 2022). This scenario is not likely to generate any kind of self-limitation. On the contrary: it facilitates the expansion of humorous practices which, as Herrera Moreno (2020) states, are conditioned by the very characteristics of modern communication, where the profitability of digital attention is increasingly predominant—with growing doses of brutalism, egotism and extreme humour to facilitate the maximisation of followers on social media networks in a context of high competitiveness and almost no regulation. All of this happens, Habermas states in one of his recent works, at the cost of reducing public space to a conversation with low levels of reflexivity and little responsible deliberation (Habermas, 2022).

It is worth asking whether, in addition to specific rulings by the judicial system, other alternatives might be possible to guarantee an ethics of humour responsibility. A first option would be legislation that allows for out-of-court adjudication of potentially toxic humorous content, as proposed by the Digital Services Act⁶ (DSA) at the European level, without forgetting the technical and regulatory difficulties posed by content moderation on large online platforms (Alkiviadou, 2022; Godioli et al., 2022; Nunziato, 2023). In this sense, it would also be important to discuss the liability of intermediaries, that is, the extent to which social media platforms should be held responsible for harmful content (Matamoros-Fernandez et al., 2023). A second option would be the increase of counterspeech initiatives (Ullman & Tomalin, 2014) against socially divisive humour practices, through dissuasive measures of various kinds, as happened in 2007 with the famous American journalist Don Imus, who, after making an offensive humorous comment towards a women’s basketball team, had to resign from his job after an intense campaign of economic boycott against the media company he worked for (Poniewozik, 2007). This is also an ambivalent example, one that shows the importance of republican social awareness, but one that also contrasts with current accusations about the dangers of censorship and the culture of cancellation (Sapiro, 2021). Finally, a third option would be a greater self-regulation of the collective of comedians themselves, who can approve ethical codes that serve the constitution of an ethics of humour responsibility, while at the same time allowing for the questioning of some unprofessional attitudes and exceptionally unfortunate comic situations.

The case of Anónimo García and his *Wolf Group Tour* went through the judicial route from the very beginning. In fact, as noted above, his humorous action overlapped in a very unfortunate way with the days in which the rape victim was awaiting the judicial ruling on her rapists, which further aggravated her discomfort. This initial lack of sensitivity on the part of Anónimo García, together with the social unrest with which his satirical action was received, undoubtedly contributed to the immediate closure of the website by the author himself, which demonstrated his mistake. It also demonstrated the existence of a civic culture in Spain, one that ethically rejected dealing humorously with such a delicate matter as the rape of a real person, offering a kind of common sense about what is unacceptable. After the first three court rulings against Anónimo García, the expressions of solidarity towards him focused mainly on criticising the rulings as such, the disproportionality of the penalty and the possibility of going to prison, but there have been fewer expressions of understanding towards his humorous action. Among the

⁶ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digital-services-act-package>

world of comedians, in fact, he has found practically no support. The ideologically confused character of Anónimo García, his somewhat hooliganish, iconoclastic spirit, and his distance from the world of professional humour, have certainly not helped him to find public support. After the TC's annulment, there has also been no full assessment of this satirical action. In an interview Anónimo García gave to Spain's most influential radio station two days after the TC's ruling, journalists congratulated him for avoiding prison but asked him if he had ever considered that his satirical action should have taken the rape victim into greater consideration. The coldness with which he avoided answering this question left journalists and listeners somewhat perplexed.⁷

As the criminologist Herrera Moreno states, the contemporary criminal legal model is today trapped between a punitive populism and a logic of slow legal formality that limits the understanding of the type of accelerated society in which we live in and, therefore, limits the search for suitable solutions to cases such as the one we are dealing with here: "the decline of 'slow' attentional styles, which would facilitate critical introspection and discernment between creators and users, fatally stalk criminal law, whose textual mandates have a very doubtful chance of influence in the carnival of the Internet" (Herrera Moreno, 2021: 456-457). From a criminal point of view, the case of Anónimo García can be seen as someone who has simply played at pushing the boundaries of the law with such a powerful tool as digital humour. From a more sociological point of view, on the other hand, this case can (and should) be seen as a symptomatic example of a more or less ingenious person who has had a great moment of digital notoriety through a highly invasive comic action, able to attract the spasmodic attention (Hayles, 2007) of a large number of digital users. Anónimo García believed that the potential harm that this action could produce "is directly assumed as a necessary consequence for the scope of the criticism" (Herrera Moreno, 2021, p. 453). That is to say, the potential harm is accepted as an insignificant marginal cost; they are, as Walter Benjamin proclaimed in his *Thesis on the Concept of History* published in 1940, the inevitable corpses on the road to progress designed by the winners of modernity (Benjamin, 2021, p. 69-71).

In this sense, if it were possible to 'judge' the satirical action of Anónimo García without winners and losers, with tools that go beyond punitive penal parameters and seek a kind of restorative justice (Herrera Moreno, 2012), it would be important to assume that (i) we are not in this case dealing with a criminal for whom a prison sentence would be the best solution, but (ii) it would be also important to demand from the author of the website a clear and unequivocal social reparation beyond the economic one for the harm caused to the victim as a necessary condition to demonstrate that he recognises the importance of a minimum ethics of responsibility when practicing satire. That is, recognising the need for a reparation process that makes a community a dignified place where cruelty is rejected. Unfortunately, the absence of this intermediate option has led the judicial process to a zero-sum solution: either the comedian wins or the victim wins.

7. Conclusion

Strange as it may seem, the court rulings in the case of *Wolf Group Tour* until the resolution provided by the TC remained completely silent about the limits of freedom of speech that a satirist has in a democratic society. Implicitly, they had argued that this freedom cannot be invoked when a humorous action causes physical and mental harm to a specific person. As some jurists had pointed out (Cigüela, 2021; Cuerda, 2021), it was foreseeable that this lack of argumentation by the judges would be criticised by the Constitutional Court, and indeed it was. Perhaps this case has been a missed opportunity for the courts to offer insights into the extent to

⁷ The complete interview can be accessed in <https://cadenaser.com/audio/1747240095330/>

which some humorous expression can be imaginatively penalised (maybe a need for a type of “comedic civic service” as punishment?), taking into account factors such as, for example, the health status of the target, the inappropriateness of satirising at very specific times or the irresponsible lack of regret. The question, however, is whether the criminal route was the most appropriate response to impart justice.

That being said, in the sphere of the public opinion, the case offers sufficient evidence that Anónimo García has treated the content of his satire irresponsibly. Perhaps he thought that his ethical responsibilities were towards humour and not towards the alleged victim. Perhaps he believed that humour has no specific victims, but the truth is that it does. In his current statements he continues to cling to the idea that the website is virtual but not real (as if these two terms were incompatible, but they are not), that the Tour “did not exist” when in fact it did. In short, he seems to lack a minimal desire to make amends towards the victim.

Common sense tells us that it is practically impossible to imagine humorous practices that everyone would like. However, comedians should aspire to produce something that, in any case, would minimise the pain and harm to certain particularly vulnerable individuals or groups, clearly in special cases, where ambiguity does not help but rather aggravates their discomfort. In these special cases, common sense developed by means of public debates, self-reflexivity, ethical awareness and honest openness to dialogue would advise establishing a social limit on what is not laughable, aiming to avoid causing additional harm to vulnerable individuals or groups. It remains to be seen whether this sentimental education of humorous common sense is the job of judges or is a task for public opinion. The case of Anónimo García offers some clues to affirm that, if the work of judges and public opinion are not aligned, then the punitive work of the judicial system will reduce the possibilities of restorative justice, and that “grey zone of legitimate dissent” (Nunner-Winkler, 2020, p. 184) where we could agree to reject cruelty will become a very narrow one. In this context of increased judicialisation, the sacred apostles of humour -convinced that they are waging a crusade in favour of humour and freedom of expression—find it difficult to fit into this grey zone, among other things because they expel from that public space the healthy scepticism of a truly inclusive humour.

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